

The Outcomes of Respiratory Support and Anti-Covid Therapy on Covid-19 Patients in the Special Isolation Room – Intensive Care Unit at Dr. Soetomo General Hospital

Anton Abadi^{*1}, Christrijogo Sumartono¹, Erwin Triyono Astha¹, Windhu Purnomo¹, Arie Utariani¹, and Nancy Margarita Rehatta¹

¹ Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Faculty of Medicine Airlangga University, Dr Soetomo General Hospital, Surabaya, Indonesia

Abstract:- Background: An ongoing research of therapy COVID-19 has different outcomes, especially in critical care. We aimed to described outcomes of respiratory support and anti-COVID combination on COVID-19 patient in intensive care unit.

Methods: This single-centered, retrospective, observational study, we enrolled 68 critically ill who were admitted to the Intensive Care Unit in the Special Isolation Room of Dr. Soetomo General Hospital, Surabaya between May-October 2020. Demographic data, respiratory support, anti-COVID, length of stay and mortality were all collected through medical record.

Results: A total 68 patient were included. The mean age of the patients was 49.19 years (SD 11.05), 19 (27.9%) were men, 42 (61.8 %) has chronic illness, 38 (55.9%) patients had died, the median duration for admission to the intensive care unit (ICU) with survivor 9 days (IQR 6-17). Respiratory support with HFNC were 21 patients (30.9%), Ventilator 36 patient (52.9%), combination HFNC and Ventilator 11 patients (16.2 %). Patients who received lopinavir/ritonavir were 43 (63.2 %) and hydrochloroquine 25 (36.8%). The mean p/f ratio day 3 was 136.27 (SD 63.93), CRP 10.88 mg/L (SD 8.23), IL-6 208.79 pg/mL (SD 529.03). Compare with survivors, non survivors who received HFNC were 3 patients (14.3 %) vs 18 patients (85.7%), mechanical ventilator 31 patients (86.1%) vs 5 patients (13.9%), combination HFNC and mechanical ventilator 4 patients (36.4%) vs 7 patients (63.6%), within who receive HCQ mortality was 17 patients (44.7%) vs 8 patients (26.7%) and lopinavir/ritonavir 21 patients (55.7%) vs 22 patients (73.3%).

Conclusion: The mortality of COVID-19 patients in ICU is considerable. Patients who receive HFNC has better outcome and lower mortality because of lower degree of disease severity. A further large-scale, prospective, and multicenter study is necessary.

Keywords:- COVID-19, length of stay, anti-COVID, respiratory support, mortality.

I. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 as a global pandemic has been a problem in global scale [1]. Mortality is related with respiratory support

requirement due to acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). High demand of ICU care, the management and holistic standard therapy of critical care are needed. The definitive therapy of COVID-19 has not been clearly implemented as the research are still ongoing. Antiviral therapy used based on experience of previous pandemic (SARS and MERS) shows different outcome, especially in critical case [2]. One of the most essential for COVID-19 patients was use of respiratory support. High-flow nasal cannule (HFNC) is widely used for COVID-19 patients, especially in mild to moderate hypoxemic conscious patient [3]. If HFNC is still not adequate, intubation for mechanical ventilation takes place. The severity level COVID-19 ranges from mild to critically ill. Therefore, this research was conducted to describe the outcome of respiratory support and anti-COVID of COVID-19 patient in intensive care on Special Isolation Room of Dr. Soetomo General Hospital.

II. METHODS

This single-center, retrospective observational study was done at Dr. Soetomo General Hospital (Surabaya, Indonesia). All patients with age above 18 years old, positively confirmed for COVID-19, and admitted to intensive care unit (ICU) in the period of May to October of 2020 were included. The included patients were treated with respiratory support (high-flow nasal cannule, mechanical ventilator, and combination of both) and anti-COVID (hydrochloroquine and lopinavir/ritonavir) medication. We excluded pregnant women and patients who were given plasma convalescence therapy. Observational study was reviewed and approved by the research institutional review board and granted permission by the director of hospital to collect data from medical records.

We collected data on age, sex, chronic illness (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, coronary disease) for all patients with laboratory confirmed COVID-19. Laboratory values collected in day-3 admission were p/f ratio, CRP and IL-6. The primary outcome was mortality after ICU admission and length of stay in ICU.

The aim of this study was to report outcome and laboratory findings of COVID-19 patients in ICU of Dr. Soetomo General Hospital during the study period. We expressed descriptive data age as mean (SD), length of stay as median (IQR), laboratory findings as number and % for categorical variables. We analyzed combination of

respiratory support and anti-COVID for mortality and length of stay.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

From May to October 2020, a total of 68 out of 76 PCR-positive COVID-19 patients in intensive care isolation wards of Dr. Soetomo General Hospital, Surabaya were included in this study. Patients’ age ranged from 18 to 65 years old. Subject characteristics included age, sex, comorbidities, length of stay in intensive care unit, CRP serum level, IL-6 serum level (Table 1). The subjects were grouped, based on use of respiratory support devices (HFNC or ventilator or combined respiratory support) and anti-COVID drugs (HCQ or Lopi/Ritonavir) (Figure 1).

In our study, patients who received lopinavir/rotinavir and HFNC had the shortest length of stay among 6 groups (7.63 ± 5.23 days; p =.04) and the greatest survival among 6 groups (16/19 [84.2%]; p=.00), further illustrated in Table 2. The difference of mortality rates in our study might be caused by our method of grouping, which was based on combination of lopinavir-ritonavir and HFNC. Patients on HFNC often had milder hypoxemia. The lower degree of disease severity on patients who receive HFNC might contribute to the shorter length of stay and greater survival.

Most COVID-19 patients were admitted to intensive care unit in a state of respiratory failure. Tracheal intubation was needed in 88% of the patients, especially the ones who needed high PEEP. Noninvasive respiratory support was needed in 11% of the patients, although some could be admitted to intermediate ward [4]. HFNC could decrease ventilator use, sedation drugs use, delirium, and paralysis. Use of HFNC is also beneficial when hypoxemia can be treated without tracheal intubation, leading to efficient use of resources and intensive care equipment. HFNC is easier to use and recommended as first-line respiratory support for COVID-19 patients with hypoxemia [5]. In a randomized study by Grieco et al., there was no difference of length of stay in 110 patients with NIV helmet or high-flow nasal oxygen (95%CI, -2 to 6; P = .26), but endotracheal intubation and ventilator use were decreased [6]. Use of HFNC can improve hypoxemia. With spontaneous breathing, high PEEP can increase FRC and decrease respiratory effort, tidal volume, and irregular breathing pattern. HFNC also prevents ventilator-associated infections. A similar study by Rochweg et al. also did not found any significant difference on mortality between HFNC and conventional oxygen therapy (RR 0.94, 95% confidence interval [CI] 0.67–1.31). Use of HFNC improved hypoxemia but did not decrease the duration of respiratory support (1.38 days longer, 95% CI 0.90 - 3.66). The use of high-flow nasal oxygen decreased the use of invasive ventilator (RR 0.85, 95% CI 0.74–0.9). However, the study had bias on unclear benefits of HFNC due to small sample size and separated results on a number of patient groups. The hypothesis of the study stated that HFNC has a potential benefit of limiting lung damage, decreasing

desynchronization, and adjusting the patient’s respiratory flow needs, compared with invasive respiratory support [5].

A study by Cao et al. showed that lopinavir-ritonavir did not affect mortality rates (19.2% vs. 25.0%; -5.8 %; 95% CI, -17.3 to 5.7) and respiratory support use, but decreased length of ICU stay (median 6 vs. 11 days; -5 days; 95% CI, -9 to 0). The study found increased gastrointestinal effects (e.g. nausea, vomitus, and diarrhea) with lopinavir-ritonavir. A proportion of 14% in lopinavir-ritonavir group did not complete the therapy due to serious side effects. However, lopinavir-ritonavir decreased AKI, secondary infection, and respiratory support need compared with those who did not receive lopinavir-ritonavir. The study did not show decreased viral RNA load compared with standard therapy. The stated benefits of lopinavir-ritonavir on the study have to be further studied and are not applicable to general population of COVID-19 patients. The study had several limitations, including unblinded method and confounding variables, such as glucocorticoid use, were not included [7]. A similar study by WHO Solidarity Trial Consortium also compared remdesivir, lopinavir-ritonavir, and HCQ and found no difference in mortality rates [8].

Limitation of our study was high bias in determining COVID-19 patients due to the retrospective design of the study. Severity of COVID-19 also tended to be much higher in patients who received ventilators and combined respiratory support than those who received HFNC.

Characteristics	Mean ± SD	Median (IQR)	N(%)
Age (years)	49.19 ± 11.05		
Sex			
Male			19(27,9)
Female			49(72.1)
Chronic medical illness			
Present		9 (6-17)	42(61.8)
Absent			26(38.2)
Length of ICU stay (days)	136.26 ± 63.93		
p/f Ratio	10.88 ± 8.23)		
CRP	208.79 ±		21(30.9)
IL-6	529.03		36(83.8)
HFNC			11(16.2)
Mechanical Ventilator			25 (36.8)
Combination Respiratory			43(63.2)
HCQ			
Lopinavir/ritonavir			

Table 1: Subjects characteristics

Fig. 1: Grouping based on anti-COVID drugs and respiratory support devices

Group	Mean	SD	p-value	HCQ + Ventilator vs Lo/Rito + Combination	Lo/Rito + HFNC vs Lo/Rito + Combination	Lo/Rito + Ventilator vs Lo/Rito + Combination
HCQ + HFNC	9.00	11.314	0,041	0,037	0,002	0,036
HCQ + Ventilator	10.79	5.381				
HCQ + Combination	11.75	6.238				
Lo/Rito + HFNC	7.63	5.230				
Lo/Rito + Ventilator	12.18	11.980				
Lo/Rito + Combination	17.43	7.368				

Table 2: Length of stay

*Kruskal-Wallis test

Group	Death	Survive	p-value
HCQ + HFNC	0 (0,0%)	2 (6,7%)	0,000
HCQ + Ventilator	15 (39,5%)	4 (13,3%)	
Respiratory support combination	2 (5,3%)	2 (6,7%)	
Lopi/ritonavir + HFNC	3 (7,9%)	16 (53,3%)	
Lop/ritonavir + Ventilator	16 (42,1%)	1 (3,3%)	
Lop/ritonavir + combination	2 (5,3%)	5 (16,7%)	

Table 3: Mortality rates

*Chi-Square test

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, patients who received high-flow nasal oxygen therapy and lopinavir/ritonavir had shorter length of stay and lower COVID-19 mortality rates in intensive care. However, this finding may be due to the lower degree of disease severity in patients who received HFNC. Further studies with adequate sample size and prospective design are needed to determine the true effects of anti-COVID drugs and respiratory support devices.

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